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The Potential of Restorative Approaches in Domestic Violence Cases to Contribute to More Victim-Centred Responses – Based on the Experiences of Two Field-based Research Programs

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The article aims to discuss the opportunities for a restorative approach in domestic violence (DV) cases based on the results of two empirical research. After describing the victims' perspective, we introduce the shortcomings of institutional frontline responses that hinder the effective prevention and fight against domestic violence. At the end of the paper, some local support initiatives for victims of DV are described. We examine the aspects of these initiatives that bring them close to the restorative approach – although they do not explicitly label themselves as restorative.

Keywords: domestic violence, restorative approach, frontline responders, Hungary, IMPROVE, IMPRODOVA.

Introduction

Our paper aims to discuss the opportunities of a restorative approach in domestic violence (DV) cases, where women victims are concerned, within the framework of two empirical research focusing on how frontline responders

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(from the legal, social and health sectors) react to domestic violence. Firstly, based on various Hungarian studies we introduce the victims' perspective, and examine to what extent frontline responses resonate appropriately with victims' needs. Then, we introduce the idea of handling DV cases with restorative justice (RJ), involving international literature. Finally, we examine some Hungarian initiatives following a restorative approach alongside several criteria that are key for victim-centred processes: thorough assessment of cases, active participation and engagement of the victims, involvement of all stakeholders, ensuring a safe space and empowerment by trust and the dialogue process. As we argue, these practices have the potential to satisfy victims' needs and even counterbalance systemic, institutional deficiencies.

Experiences of victims of domestic violence

The IMPROVE¹ program, which started at the end of 2022 with the participation of eight countries, members of the European Union (EU), aims primarily to increase the reporting and detection of domestic violence, to enhance the competencies of frontline responders (FLRs), and to empower victims to understand their rights to services and justice. DV has different definitions based on the group of victims that violence concerns as well as the type and volume of violence. The main victim group that our program targeted were women victims of intimate partner violence. Within the first phase of the program, our research team conducted a literature review on domestic violence. We reviewed the factors that influence the likelihood that victims report domestic violence, and seek services and support from frontline responders. In addition, we analysed the victims' sociocultural characteristics, social and economic disadvantages, perceptions of frontline response and services, and the real opportunities offered by the service structure as well. It is worth mentioning that Hungarian publications under investigation usually introduce feedback from frontline responders and social scientists (Sándor, 2016; Hornyik, 2020; Windt, 2020; Hegyi, 2022; Hera, 2022; Nagy, Petrus 2022) and provide summaries about findings of document analysis (Farkas, 2013; Garai, 2019; Solt, 2022). Therefore, the experiences of the victims were often presented only in

¹ IMPROVE project is funded by the European Union under HORIZON Innovation Actions (Grant Agreement No. 101074010). More information about the project is available here: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101074010>.

an indirect way. However, we decided to follow a different strategy here and present briefly the research reports that involve and give voice to women victims themselves (Czibere, 2012; Human Rights Watch, 2013; Nagy et al., 2020).

It might be important to mention that these reports do not make a difference between different types of violence; they do not differentiate between intimate terrorism and common (or situational) couple violence (Johnson, 1995). In both cases, perpetrators and victims usually know each other and live in the same household. However, the latter form of violence is quite prevalent, two-sided, not (necessarily) repeated and escalating, not driven by the desire to control the other (Pemberton et al., 2009) and is not predominantly committed by men (Graham-Kevan, Archer, 2003). In this case, socio-economic circumstances (such as poverty, poor social status, and bad housing conditions) or individual mental issues are in the background as causes. The above-mentioned research reports describe solely the characteristics of intimate terrorism, where coercive control exists in the relationships. In this case, victims are often monitored and controlled by the abusers. In addition, they are deprived of independence and even of their basic needs. They are not only typically separated from their family and friends, but they cannot even reach support services. Isolation is more severe when offenders successfully harm the victim's reputation and when intimidation is so strong that asking for help itself seems life-threatening. It might be important to mention here, that the COVID-19 lockdown, when the constant coexistence of the victim and the abuser increased tension in the relationships and within families, intensified the sense of isolation. During this period, NGOs reported an increased frequency of violent acts, higher numbers of crisis hotline calls and demand for secret shelter placement (Hera, Szego, 2023).

As the research reports (Czibere, 2012; Human Rights Watch, 2013; Nagy et al., 2020) highlight, victims of intimate terrorism suffer from ongoing physical and verbal insults. The continuous threat, intimidation and oppression diminishes their confidence and self-esteem. They often take the view that their own behaviour is the deep-rooted cause of the violence. Some of them even suppose that changes in their attitudes and behaviour might improve the situation in their abusive relationships, and cease violence and oppression. Thus, victims often feel that they are to be blamed (at least partially) for the abuse as well as for bearing the violence. Self-blaming is reinforced by feelings of shame and failure – and sometimes even by the community

network of the victims as well. Members of this network often represent traditional gender and family norms and strengthen the classical roles, duties, and responsibilities of the family members. According to this approach, husband and wife raise their kids together in unity. Women are typically in a subordinated position. They are expected to be self-sacrificing, loving and understanding towards their husbands, and they are supposed to forgive them for their violent acts. At the same time, women keep the family together. A kind of 'romantic interpretation', which legitimizes violence, could be also identified. According to this discourse, men cause trouble only because of the love that blinds them. If two people love each other, it takes only some time for the relationship to mend itself, and spouses, partners will enjoy the same closeness as before. As a consequence, members of the informal network often try to convince the victims to endure violence and abuse. This simplified approach of gender roles not only implies victim blaming but also ignores the complexity of cases and possible victim-offender roles by picturing a typical victim and offender character, which is far from the everyday realities of domestic violence situations.

Besides the lack of support from community members, according to Hungarian studies, occasionally the police do not show sensitivity and do not acknowledge that victims are abused and thus have trauma-related difficulties. These officers cannot recognise and understand the needs of the victims in the key moment when support would be crucial, sometimes even life-saving. Victims complain about police officers who take the police report but do nothing. As one of the interviewees of the research conducted by Human Rights Watch (2013: 33) put it: "I called the police many times to tell them to do something as my husband was threatening violence [...] They always told me that they can't do anything unless blood flows". Another victim complains about police officers who take the perpetrator to the police office but release him the next day (Human Rights Watch, 2013: 27). Others are afraid of male officers who probably side with men, do not believe the victims and even put them under pressure rather than the offender. Sometimes victims have to explain to the uncomprehending officers why they have previously not left their abusive partners. The study reports about officers who asked the victim not to call the police again as they had to intervene too many times. Due to certain characteristics of the victims, such as fear, dependency and the dynamics of violence, victims usually are either reluctant to file a complaint against

the offender, or they are likely to cancel their testimonies and withdraw their complaints already in the investigation phase. The investigation process is typically long and bureaucratic, which discourages the victims from further maintaining their testimonies – which can be easily condemned by police officers.

To sum up, victims suffering from the harms of abusive relationships often lack the support of their community members and the police. There is a chance that reporting domestic violence and being involved in official criminal procedures cause further traumatic stress, and mental disorder and might result in secondary victimisation.

Perspectives of frontline responders

In this chapter, we primarily build upon the research findings of the IMPRODOVA research project that was designed to provide solutions for an integrated response to domestic violence. Among many other activities, our team collected information about the domestic violence-related curriculum in education and conducted empirical fieldwork as well.

The Hungarian team conducted 32 semi-structured interviews with police officers (16) and social workers (16) in two locations in 2019. Our primary aim was to reveal the main challenges and shortcomings characterising the work of frontline responders while preventing and responding to domestic violence. As soon as we received permission from the National Headquarters of the Hungarian Police to carry out interviews, participating police officers were selected from the local Investigation Departments and Violent Crimes Units. In addition, the crime prevention advisors were also interviewed. When it comes to the social sector, leaders of the local institutions, i.e., crisis centres, secret shelters, temporary homes for families and child protection services permitted us to conduct interviews with their colleagues. The minimum length of the interviews was around half an hour, while the longest conversation took more than three and a half hours. The average length of the interviews was around an hour. All of the 32 interviews were recorded and transcribed. While analysing the qualitative data, we followed the steps of thematic analysis (Braun, Clarke, 2006; Moira, Brid, 2017). At the end of the process, we managed to identify patterns and themes that described the nature of interagency cooperation, the way DV cases are detected, the

process of filing a complaint, the obstacles the victims face, the procedures that can give an immediate and effective response to the victims, and, in addition, the frontline responders' attitudes towards domestic violence cases.

As we recognised, several circumstances hinder frontline responders from giving immediate and appropriate support to DV victims. The problem starts with education. The curriculum analysis revealed that the amount of time dedicated to DV throughout the basic training of police officers is insufficient. We could identify only a very few DV-related lessons and courses that were usually not dedicated explicitly to the topic. Even if DV is discussed, typically only the relevant legal framework and institutional conditions are introduced by the teachers and lecturers. During the empirical fieldwork, we met some police officers who took part in further training programs about restraining orders, learnt about the psychological dimensions and the legal environment of DV and got acquainted with the circumstances that should be taken into consideration when a restraining order is applied by the police officers. Others underlined that some other trainings on empathy and communication, about children interviewing techniques, were also available for police officers. However, these courses do not directly address DV and do not improve the skills that are necessary for recognising DV incidents and providing sufficient support for the victims. Police officers could not gain practical work experience as part of their basic education and further training. As a result, police officers patrolling the street may not be able to identify various forms of DV. The lack of proper education probably explains why police officers did not seem to have detailed background knowledge about the mechanisms of DV. One of our interviewees even expressed the difficulties in understanding why women did not break the circle of violence: "It is very difficult for me to handle how can someone, who has been hit two or three times go back for a fourth". In addition, some of the police officers are frustrated because of the cancellation of the criminal procedure by the victims themselves. As a result, negative attitudes towards the victims might be formed and reinforced within the system.

The system that aims at protecting victims seems to function well only from the perspective of police protocols and official measures. When violence between family members is reported, police officers react on time and arrive on the spot. Active measures help to maximize victim detection and protection. First of all, it is necessary to identify the signs of crisis and violence (visible injuries caused by physical violence, emotional state of the victim, the

victim reporting multiple aggressive incidents, etc.). In case violence is suspected, measures include not only separating the offender and providing information to the victims (e.g. about the opportunities to ensure their safety) but, if necessary, even the relocation of endangered victims to the shelters. However, the effectiveness of these measures largely depends on the competencies, skills and experiences of the responding police officers. In fact, many times these competencies are missing – because of a lack of education and knowledge about the mechanisms of DV. Victim-blaming attitudes and stereotypes about offenders and victims make it harder to initiate the official procedure that can give immediate, often life-saving responses for urgent needs. As one of the interviewees from the social sector described, one of his clients was convinced by a police officer not to apply for a restraining order as initiating such a process requires (too much) administration and time. Somebody else emphasized that police react only if injuries of physical violence can be observed on the spot. As another interviewee from the social sector put it:

“It happened before that a victim went to the police to file a complaint about DV, and they sent her away, saying that they thought she would change her mind later and would not keep her testimony. [...] It happened not once that the police officers told the victims to think it over one more time and come back if they were still convinced that they wanted to file a complaint.”

It might be important to mention here that some frontline responders in Hungary identify with traditional conservative family values and roles attached to them. It is not uncommon that FLRs argue that some forms of aggressive behaviour are acceptable in certain situations from men. Simplifying perceptions of victim-offender situations by FLRs hinder effective answers that react to the complicated and diverse realities of the victims of domestic violence.

Due to traumatization of the victims and re-traumatization that is caused by the potentially inadequate response of the police officers, social workers have a more crucial role in supporting victims of domestic violence. However, the number of courses that deal with DV or related topics and are available for social workers at universities is minimal. It seems that a coherent, unified curriculum or discussion on domestic violence is lacking in social work education. The topic of violence against children and women exists, but not in a particular place within the courses. It is mostly described or mentioned in

the frame of child protection and family dynamics. If the subject of violence appears within an existing course, it usually comes in the form of a general and undetailed 1.5-hour presentation. The in-service trainings have lately been supported by NGOs and colleagues of the National Crisis Telephone Information Service helpline as well. A further learning platform mentioned by the social workers is professional exchanges among the shelters, which take place either in the form of institution visits or 1-2-day long workshops. However, most of the social workers with whom we got in contact during the fieldwork, learned specific knowledge about domestic violence through experience in the field.

Appropriate attention, support and protection are hindered even by some structural weaknesses as well; especially administrative burdens and high workload, fluctuation, absence of supervision and burnout.

Restorative approach for victims of domestic violence

The application of restorative justice in DV cases is often criticised. Some scholars, researchers and practitioners express doubts, and underline possible dangers of 'cheap justice' (Coker, 1999: 85) and 'gambling with lives and safety' (Cameron, 2006: 59). However, others believe that it can be an effective option that has the potential to support victims of domestic violence, and even offenders because it might be able to balance the weaknesses of the institutional system and improve the way frontline responders react to DV (Curtis-Fawley, Daly, 2005; Fernandez, 2010; Pelikan, 2010; Jülich, Landon, 2017; Marsh, Wager, 2015; McGlynn et al., 2017). The picture is not entirely clear due to the limited number of rigorous, peer-reviewed and evidence-based evaluations (Ptacek, Frederick, 2008; Gang et al., 2019), and because we often do not know restorative justice programmes as they are implemented 'under the radar' (Keenan et al., 2016: 105) in some countries.

While collecting empirical data within the framework of the IMPRODOVA program, we also got in contact with a crisis ambulance², a secret shelter and

² Prevention is the core task of these organisations; professionals want to handle conflicts and family issues before severe violence occurs. Crisis ambulances provide information, legal and psychological counselling and further workshops, and training.

a halfway house³ where some elements of the restorative approach can be detected. We interviewed a leader of a crisis ambulance who tried to implement the restorative approach into their organisation. She considered the organisation as restorative because:

“The service is designed to prevent tragedies and serious critical life situations. It is precisely to identify problematic situations and to repair and prevent further harm in time. So, in this sense, we can say that the whole service is kind of restorative. Because it is not that something has already happened and you react to that. For example, you report it to the police, you try to escape from the abusive relationship and divorce. Instead, you try to understand the problem, look for the facts and see how you can fix the situation before escalation.”

Hereby, we identify some further characteristics of the victim support practices that can be labelled as restorative, which is presented in the text that follows.

Restorative response based on a thorough assessment

When a client asks for help in the crisis ambulance, professionals conduct a thorough assessment of the case. During this process, social workers of the institution put weight on understanding the situation together with the clients, alongside restorative questions, such as: What happened? What has led to the situation? What do you think you need to make things right for you? These questions are asked within the framework of appropriate preparation. As a consequence, professionals are aware of the antecedents of the relationship and the violence. They carefully consider the participants, their abilities and their willingness to take part in any dialogue processes, which aim at sensitising the abuser to the victims' perspective and creating safe spaces to discuss their issues. Meeting these requirements is extremely important in cases where the

³ Victims and persons living in the same household in crisis due to domestic violence can be accommodated in crisis centres (maximum for eight weeks) and secret shelter homes (maximum for 6 months). Professionals of these institutions provide help in managing psychological injuries of abuse and giving legal advice to protect the interests of the victim. In order to provide accommodation and services for the victims from the sixth month onwards, the crisis centre may provide halfway house services as a supplementary activity. These institutions ensure accommodation, help needed in life management and support the social reintegration of the victim for the abused family leaving the shelter home (maximum for 5 years).

victim suffers from anxiety-related problems and post-traumatic stress disorder, which makes it difficult for them to express their needs and wishes.

When assessing the situation of a victim, an emphasis is put on revealing the nature of violence as well. Possession and control is a crucial form of violence described by some of the interviewees as: “when the abuser declares what the victim has to do [...] In this case, the abuser does not see himself and the way he behaves. And we, the professionals, will not have access to him. From that type of relationship, as a professional, I also say that the victim has to escape and disappear as soon as possible.” It can be concluded that social workers at the institutions under investigation are aware of different variations of violence and can differentiate between intimate terrorism and common (or situational) couple violence (Johnson, 1995) which has been already described in this chapter. According to the majority opinion of our interviewees, there is an opportunity for the professionals to apply restorative justice techniques solely in the latter case (although, the RJ approach and processes can satisfy the needs of victims under coercive control even at a later stage in their healing process if victims wish to communicate with their former abusive partner in safe settings).

Active participation and agency of the victims

Active participation of the clients is ensured during the process. Social workers try to work out a liveable scenario together with the clients, talking through all various alternative decisions and their outputs, e.g., a possible judicial complaint, judicial procedure and its risks. Returning to the violent perpetrator as a possible decision is not a taboo or a scenario the social workers would disapprove. There is an opportunity within the organisation that we examined to discuss with the victim even that option with its consequences. They believe that if they consider a scenario together, enable the agency of the clients, and do not make decisions for them but with them, the clients will feel ownership over their decisions. As one of our interviewees put it, it is important to: “teach the victims not to take the role of the victims all the time and it is important to keep their boundaries. So, the more they do not keep their boundaries and allow certain things to happen, the more often they will be hurt.”

Involvement of all the stakeholders

While searching for solutions, the victim and the professionals may decide to involve even the perpetrators in the process. One of our interviewees shared with us her experiences with such a case:

“First, the wife came to me separately and it turned out that the conflicts were partly caused by the husband’s relatively regular drinking. But the wife also said that she doesn’t always talk to her husband the way she should. And we met the husband, first separately, who also thought that they both communicated relatively violently with each other. And so, they had expressed that they wanted to improve their situation because they were emotionally connected. The aim was to resolve conflict situations without violence, to learn new techniques, and to learn how to do things when tensions escalate so that they don’t fall out, and don’t jump down each other’s throats. Because there were examples of even physical confrontations and police action. There was an element when they said that they could not yet sit down with me. But they would like something to change in terms of how they could communicate with each other without violence, so finally, they came for a relatively long time and regularly.”

As our interviewees underlined, parties – victims, members of their surrounding communities and abusers as well – can be involved in dialogue processes only if voluntariness is guaranteed. This approach is described by one of the social workers who underlined that: “we always wait for them to volunteer. They shouldn’t feel that there is an agency or a professional putting pressure on them and thus they are obligated to participate.” Another crucial requirement of practice is avoidance of stigmatisation because: “if the abusers are labelled as guilty, the situation is getting worse as they become resistant and would not like to cooperate.” Of course, social professionals consider the needs of the victims as well: dialogue with the abusers can be realized only if violence does not go on, victims’ safety and voluntary participation are fully guaranteed, and there is enough time for careful preparation of the meeting.

Practitioners at the crisis centre we interviewed are aware that there may not be a supportive community surrounding the victims and thus it might not be possible to engage offenders and members of the informal network. This practice is in line with the research findings of scholars and recommendations

of RJ professionals. According to Coker (2002), the community can give genuine support to the victims only if it owns a type of morality. Pemberton and his co-authors also underline that it is false to consider a community that is based on informal relationships 'as inevitably benign or by its nature less punitive or more humanitarian' (Pemberton et al., 2007: 29). If members of the community do not consider sexual abuse and domestic violence unacceptable or if they have mixed loyalties towards the victims and offenders (Daly, Stubs, 2006; Keenan et al., 2016), then involvement can be counterproductive. Crawford and Clear (2001: 137) came to the same conclusion, underlining that communities can be: "pockets of intolerance and prejudice. They can be coercive and tolerant of bigotry and discriminatory behaviour. Weaker parties within such communities often experience them not as a home of connectedness and mutuality but as a mainspring of inequalities that sustain and reinforce relations of dependence (for example, with regard to gender roles and the tolerance of domestic violence or child abuse)."

Other authors and studies (Dzur, Olson, 2004; Dignan, 2005; Crawford, 2006) also underline the idealistic notion of (the often not clearly defined) community that sometimes does not meet reality. A further concern might arise due to the community representatives who aim at encouraging and reproducing already existing structures and hierarchies including oppressive dynamics (Cook, 2006), which also endangers the empowerment of DV victims. Fernandez (2010: 8) also underlines the importance of the contextual lens while understanding intimate partner violence as victims and abusers are nested in the micro-system of friends and family members. The social workers at the crisis centre where we conducted our interviews already met such a situation. That story illustrates the downside of embeddedness and community ties.

"The woman's husband, the perpetrator, was an influential local politician: When the shelter called the guardianship office to ask for information or initiate cooperation regarding the victim, the social worker dropped the phone call. The perpetrator was so influential in the town. After the shelter-supported period ended, they could hardly find a sublet for the family in the town. Nobody wanted to confront the powerful perpetrator. Finally, a member of the local support network found a solution: the priest rented a secret sublet that was in his name."

Social ties caused difficulties as the perpetrator was able to extend his power to the informal and formal local community actors. In this case, social workers did not make attempts to engage members of the informal network of the victim.

Safe space

Frontline responders promote a restorative approach even in the life of institutions where abused women and children are sheltered. The reason is to mitigate the negative side-effects of insufficient criminal procedures and other formal, official procedures. Long and bureaucratic judicial procedures in Hungary often do not match the needs of the victims. They have to wait for months, sometimes even years, for judicial decisions. During this time, they are extremely vulnerable to the perpetrators. Interviewees shared extreme stories when serious emotional and physical harm was caused as a consequence of the above-mentioned problems. For example, if the victim of DV is a mother who escaped with her children, if there is no temporary or permanent restraining order in effect and no criminal charge against the perpetrator, fathers have the right to visit their children in temporary homes for families. As a general protocol in these institutions, if the father claims so, the victim has to find a way to ensure the visiting rights of the father to the children outside of the institution, without any protection.

Practitioners at the crisis centre concluded that it is more reasonable to provide a framework and a safe space for father visits inside the Homes than to force the mother to leave the safe environment and meet the father outside the institution. This view led them to develop a local practice – with the expertise of the crisis ambulance – to organize assisted restorative dialogues within the institutional framework. Father visits are preceded by private, preparatory meetings with the father, organized and executed by the crisis centre. These meetings are organised with the aim of mapping risks, sensitizing the perpetrator to the situation of the victim, and discussing and approving the framework of the visit, which always has to be in accordance with the victim's needs. The victim's voluntary intention to meet the perpetrator is a crucial condition of the visit. The crisis centre carries out follow-up discussions with the children and monitors the impact of the visits on them.

Empower by trust and dialogue

We believe that the involvement of victims and perpetrators in a dialogue can happen only if the victim expresses this need. Moreover, these dialogue situations should always be aware of the power imbalance between the victim and the perpetrator. If such a dialogue happens, it serves the purpose of empowering the victim, regaining the legitimacy of her own perspective and feelings, and letting her express it in a safe, protective and guided setting. It should be avoided to seek any agreement as part of these dialogues.

While analysing the phenomena of DV and the institutional responses in the past few years, we, unfortunately, found dialogue processes in Hungary (e.g. some private mediation procedures that accompany divorce and child custody civil suit cases) that are not aware of the context, do not take account of the power imbalances and do not acknowledge the presence of violence in a relationship. Such a situation can cause further damage as the victim can be easily labelled as 'dis-functional' and 'incapable'. In this case, domestic violence victims are often left alone with their truth without supporters and are unable to represent their interests in divorce, child custody processes, and other official procedures. The restorative approach can be very helpful in these situations because of its basic premise: it does not question the victimhood but tries to take the victim from her 'victim mode' and create more balanced dialogue situations. Due to the nature of abusive dynamics and dependency, it is not always possible to create completely balanced situations, but some practitioners believe that it empowers the victim more if there is an endeavour for a safe dialogue than if there is no dialogue at all.

At the end, we would like to highlight the similarities between the restorative and trauma-informed care approaches. Trauma-informed practice aims at understanding the influence of trauma on an individual's life and the way trauma has a direct impact on that person. Trauma-informed care (TIC) focuses on the organisational level within which services are provided to clients (Knight, 2019). We believe that some core values of TIC can be identified in the practice we described above. Just to mention some of them: establishing (emotional) safety, restoring choice and control, facilitating survivors' connections and relationships with family members and communities, and strengthening survivors' style of coping instead of judging them are also seen as principles of TIC in DV context (Substance Abuse and Mental Health

Services Administration, 2014; Wilson et al., 2015). These similarities confirm that further attention should be paid to identifying how the combination of these paradigms, namely a trauma-informed restorative approach may support victims of domestic violence. Combining the two paradigms might allow practitioners to react to DV situations more effectively and to choose the approach, and related practice, which best serves the needs of the victims.

Conclusion

Our paper examined the results of two Hungarian research programs which aimed at increasing the reporting and detection of domestic violence, improving the frontline response and empowering the victims to understand their rights to services and justice. IMPROVE program explored the victims' perspective, while IMPRODOVA focused on the frontline responders. These programs identified the impact of DV on victims and the shortcomings of institutional frontline responses that hinder the effective prevention and combat against domestic violence. Although the restorative approach and practices are usually not part of the general protocols of crisis services in Hungary, we explored good practices at a crisis ambulance, a secret shelter and a halfway house, which contain elements of restorative approaches. They correspond with the restorative approach as they are based on a thorough assessment of the case, using restorative questions; they build upon active participation and agency of the victims; they strive to involve all the stakeholders voluntarily, they ensure safe space for the dialogue, and they intend to empower the victim by trust and dialogue. According to our experience of those practices that involve the above-mentioned elements, these have the potential to satisfy victims' needs better than the typical, currently existing institutional answers to domestic violence.

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Potencijal restorativnih pristupa u slučajevima porodičnog nasilja da doprinesu odgovorima usmerenim na žrtvu – Zasnovano na iskustvima dva terenska istraživačka programa

Cilj ovog rada je analiza mogućnosti primene restorativnih pristupa u slučajevima porodičnog nasilja na osnovu rezultata dva empirijska istraživanja. Nakon opisa perspektive žrtava, autori su ukazali na nedostatke institucionalnih prvih reakcija, koje otežavaju efektivnu prevenciju i suprotstavljanje nasilju u porodici. Na kraju rada su prikazane mađarske lokalne inicijative za podršku žrtvama nasilja u porodici. U vezi sa tim, autori analiziraju karakteristike ovih inicijative koje ih približavaju restorativnim pristupima, iako one sebe ne kategorišu eksplicitno kao restorativne.

Ključne reči: *nasilje u porodici, restorativni pristup, oni koji prvi odgovaraju u situacijama porodičnog nasilja, Mađarska, IMPROVE, IMPRODOVA.*

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